

WHAT WE'LL SEE DOWN

TWO PATHWAYS

TO ZERO EMISSIONS FROM BUILDINGS

Annex for LDC:

Orangeville Hydro Limited

June 2025

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The logo for the Government of Canada, featuring the word "Canada" in a large, black, serif font. A small red maple leaf is positioned above the letter "a". To the left of the word "Canada" is a vertical black line.

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This report is an Annex to the main Two Pathways report:

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1. Introduction

The Boltzmann Institute (BI), in the project “What We’ll See Down Two Pathways” (Two Pathways), has considered, compared, and made recommendations regarding two different approaches, or pathways, to (almost) eliminate GHG emissions from heating of buildings, at-scale, in communities – large and small, urban, suburban, rural and Indigenous – across Canada. For practical reasons, including data availability, most of the detailed analysis was focused on Ontario.

This Annex to the main report for the Two Pathways project presents findings and implications that are specifically relevant to the electricity local distribution company Orangeville Hydro Limited (LDC). Similar Annexes are available for 55 Ontario LDCs for which adequate data could be obtained. The Annexes are deliberately concise; full understanding of the content and implications of this Annex will depend on reading (much of) the main report, some of its references, and perhaps other Annexes (not specific to LDCs).

The information, specific to the LDC, presented here provides perspective on:

- the electrical demand that could result from electrification of building heating with air-source heat pumps (ASHP) and / or ground-source heat pumps (GSHP)
- the potential to reduce electrical demand for heating and reduce costs by implementing thermal networks (TNs) in high density areas and favouring GSHPs over ASHPs in low density areas.

The following Sections present LDC-specific data, plots, and explanations regarding:

- dwellings
- customers
- population and population density
- electrical demand by residential customers
- annual energy and peak power delivered by the LDC
- weather-related heating demand
- modeled electric power demand if heating were to be electrified.

The final Section provides discussion regarding interpretation, implications and use of the above.

2. Dwellings

Dwellings data for the LDC, derived from the 2021 Census, is shown in Table 1. Numbers were derived at the geographic level of Dissemination Blocks (DB) or postal Forward Sortation Areas (FSA) within the LDC geographic boundary published by the OEB.¹ The census divided Ontario into 137,867 DBs, with an average of 103 people per DB. There were 566, much larger, FSAs. LDC boundaries sometimes cross through an FSA, in which case the numbers shown include the total number in the FSA times the fraction of the FSA area that lies within the LDC; this can result in a minor discrepancy between the DB-level and FSA-level numbers at the LDC level due to nonuniform distribution across the FSA.²

¹ An FSA corresponds to the first three characters of a postal code.

² Statistics Canada derives FSA geometry from claimed postal codes on census responses. Because mailing

Table 1³

Dwelling type	Number	Geographic Level
Private dwellings - total	12228	DB
Private dwellings - occupied by usual residents	11957	DB
Occupied private dwellings - total	17310	FSA
Single-detached houses	12570	FSA
Semi-detached houses	1280	FSA
Row-houses	1285	FSA
Apartments in a flat or duplex	220	FSA
Apartments buildings with fewer than 5 storeys	1355	FSA
Apartments in buildings with 5 or more storeys	565	FSA
Other single-attached houses	20	FSA
Movable dwellings	15	FSA

3. Customers

Table 2 shows 2021 LDC customer counts in different rate classes from the Ontario Energy Board (OEB), and also the mean number of Residential customers in 2021 derived from FSA-level smart meter data published by the IESO.⁴

Table 2

Rate Class	Customers	Source
Residential (smart meters) – 2021 mean	10640	IESO
Residential	11483	OEB
Seasonal	0	OEB
General Service < 50 kW	1168	OEB
General Service ≥ 50 kW	124	OEB
Large User	0	OEB
Sub Transmission End Use	0	OEB

addresses sometimes differ from property location (e.g., PO boxes), the reported FSA geometries are not always accurate. That can result in errors of assignment of (parts of) FSAs to LDCs. These errors should be minor.

³ Table entries “N/A” indicate that no corresponding data was available from the standard sources.

⁴ <https://www.oeb.ca/sites/default/files/yearbook-General-Statistics-2021.xlsx>,
<https://reports-public.ieso.ca/public/HourlyConsumptionByFSA/>.

4. Population

A key challenge of the Two Pathways project was to estimate the hourly electric power demand that would result from different approaches to decarbonization of heating – various combinations of ASHPs, GSHPs, and TNs - for all buildings within each LDC. Most heating currently involves combustion of natural gas or other fuels at buildings, but the only reliable fuel consumption data that could be obtained was monthly natural gas for the whole province for the residential, commercial and industrial sectors. Data on dwellings has been presented above, but no reasonably comparable data could be obtained for commercial, institutional, or industrial buildings. As a consequence, it was necessary to make high-level approximations and develop models that use the census and other available data to best effect.

A key factor determining the viability of thermal networks in a given area is the density of heat demand (MW_{th}) per km of distribution pipe or per unit area (ha). A similar criterion applies also to natural gas distribution networks. From analysis of natural gas data (see the main Two Pathways report) it was determined that natural gas service is available to residential customers where the population density is, on average, at or above 24 people per hectare.

Recognizing that detailed analysis would be required in every case, and that different TN designs could be adopted at different densities, the simplifying assumption is made that TNs would generally be viable in the same areas that natural gas service is available. Non-residential buildings, for which data was not available, could increase the areas where TNs are viable. For specific numbers, $\rho = 24$ ppl/ha has been used as a density at which TNs are most likely viable, but low-temperature (5G) TN technology might make TNs viable at densities as low as $\rho = 10$ ppl/ha. (In some cases, a 5G TN is not much more than GSHPs with shared ground heat exchangers.)

Population data for Orangeville Hydro Limited, from the 2021 Census, is shown in Table 3. Figure 1 shows the percentage of population in the LDC living below any given density, calculated at the DB level.⁵ Figure 2 shows how the population density is distributed across the LDC, also at the DB level.

Table 3

LDC population	32598
LDC population living at density ≥ 24 people/ha	21620
Percentage in LDC of all people in Ontario living at density ≥ 24 people/ha	0.23%

⁵ The indicated area is for DBs with non-zero population, which can be less than the area of the LDC.

Figure 1. Percent of population in the LDC living below any given density ρ . Below $\rho = 10$ people/ha, properties should be large enough to install GSHPs. At $\rho = 24$ people/ha and above, TNs should be viable. Detailed analysis will be required to determine what zero-emissions heating technology would be best in the intermediate range.

People/ha - Orangeville Hydro Limited

Figure 2. Population density in the LDC using data from the 2021 Census. Unfilled areas within the LDC have zero reported population. Gray corresponds to 24 people/ha. The polygon geometry provided for some census DBs may extend over water, which causes the indicated density of the adjacent waterfront neighbourhoods to be lower than if only the land area had been included.

5. Residential Electricity Demand

The most useful and extensive data regarding electricity demand in Ontario has been obtained from the IESO.⁶ The IESO does not provide data regarding power supplied to individual LDCs, nor does it give a breakdown by customer type or rate class, except for power delivered directly to large industrial customers. However, the IESO does make available hourly data consumption reported by smart meters, aggregated at the FSA level. The smart meter data also segregates the different residential and commercial rate classes. This smart meter data has been very informative.

In cases where the number of customers on a given retail rate plan was less than a minimum group size, required to meet privacy constraints, the aggregation area was increased to the first two characters of postal codes. This occurred frequently for commercial customers and rate plans other than time-of-use

⁶ <https://reports-public.ieso.ca/public/>

(TOU), often preventing reliable allocation of data to an LDC. Consequently, the present work only made use of data for residential customers on the TOU rate plan. Analysis was further restricted to mid-week days (Tuesday, Wednesday, Thursday) that were not holidays. With the use of geographic boundary files for FSAs and LDCs, it was determined which FSAs (or fractions thereof) are contained in the LDC.

Hourly temperature data was obtained from the closest weather stations to each FSA. The thermal mass of buildings causes their heat demand to be proportional to a moving average of past temperatures instead of the instantaneous outdoor temperature. Moving average temperatures were calculated for each weather station relevant to the LDC, with the weight of the temperature t hours in the past diminishing as $\exp(-t/tc)$ in the moving averages, where tc is a time constant (in hours).

Considering each hour of day separately, electricity consumption was fitted to a model curve for different trial values of tc , allowing identification of the tc that yields the best fit to the model. Both the hourly consumption observations and the best fit curves are shown in Figure 3. The last page of this report has plots showing the statistical deviations of observed values about the best fits for each hour.

Figure 3. Average residential electricity consumption from hourly smart meter data as a function of temperature, in a different colour for each (just completed) hour of day (EST). The temperatures used are an exponential moving average as described in the text. Lines show fitted model curves.

The curves used to model electricity consumption (kWh) versus moving average temperature (T) have four segments:

- a linear (heating on) segment below a heating threshold temperature T_H , with negative slope m_H
- a short segment with constant power P_{base} (heating and cooling off) starting at T_H and extending until cooling begins at some higher temperature
- a growing quadratic segment above T_H that indicates gradual turning on of cooling
- a linear segment with positive slope m_C that begins with a smooth transition from the quadratic segment and continues at all higher temperatures.

Key parameters that characterize the linear segments of these fits are given in Table 4. The increase of power usage with dropping temperature in the heating segment will be due to an unknown combination of electric heating and electricity use by fuel-based heating systems (e.g., for blowers and pumps), plus some increment for more lighting use during the winter. The quadratic segments are believed to characterize human behaviour (personal desires for cooling) and are not relevant to the problem of heating buildings.

Table 4

Time constant of moving average temperature for best fit model of demand versus temperature	tc	18 h
Temperature below which heating is required	T_H	11.79 °C
Change in average demand per °C temperature increase when heating is needed	m_H	-0.022 kW/°C
Change in average demand per °C temperature increase when cooling is needed	m_C	0.122 kW/°C
Mean power when no heating / cooling is needed	P_{base}	0.89 kW

Variation of base power, P_{base} , through the day is indicative of daily patterns of residents and is highly consistent across the province. Even a slight lunchtime increase is evident. This is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Hourly variation of mid-week base power, P_{base} , when the temperature is such that neither heating or cooling is needed. This LDC is shown in red and all the other LDCs across Ontario in grey.

6. Heating and Cooling Degree Hours

The demand for thermal power to heat buildings is proportional to the number of degrees the moving average temperature is below the heating threshold temperature, T_H . It is common to assume some value, such as 18 C, for the heating threshold temperature, but the analysis of Section 5 used LDC-specific data to determine that $T_H = 11.79$ C for residential customers with smart meters. Lacking evidence to the contrary, the same value is assumed valid for all buildings.

While it is also common to quantify the temperature factor of heating demand in Heating Degree Days (HDD), the analysis here employs hourly data and the temperature factor will be expressed in Heating Degree Hours (HDH). Similarly, the temperature factor for cooling is expressed in terms of Cooling Degree Hours (CDH), calculated using an effective $T_c > T_H$ derived from the above fits.

The hourly heating and cooling degrees over the six-year period for which smart meter data is available are shown in Figure 5. There is clearly far greater demand for heating than for cooling. There are also substantial annual variations in both the peak and cumulative HDH and CHD.

Figure 5. Hourly heating degrees (red) and cooling degrees (blue) for the LDC over a six year period. These are based on moving average temperatures, calculated as described in the main text. Use of moving average temperatures has the effect of smoothing hourly fluctuations without changing sums over intervals a week or longer.

Key data characterizing the HDH and CDH shown in Figure 5 are listed in Table 5, with all values in degrees C.

Table 5

Mean annual Heating Degree Hours	60583
Maximum hourly heating degrees	32.8
Mean hourly heating degrees (when heating required)	11.4
Mean annual Cooling Degree Hours	3962
Maximum hourly cooling degrees	8.6
Mean hourly cooling degrees (when cooling required)	2.5

7. Power Demand for Electrified Heating

Based on data presented in the Sections above, it is possible to estimate the additional electric power demand that could result from heating decarbonization for all buildings in the LDC. Almost all of that additional demand would be for heating electrification using either ASHPs or GSHPs; TNs might also be implemented, but their electricity needs would be much less. Strategic heating planning (discussed in the main Two Pathways report) will be needed to decide on the most appropriate mix of decarbonized heating solutions in each distinct area, along with a more reliable estimate of electricity demand.

The distribution of population density shown in Section 4 indicates the percentage of dwellings at densities likely too low for TNs to be viable and that would have sufficient land available to install GSHPs. The remainder of dwellings could decarbonize heating either by installing ASHPs or by connecting to TNs (if or when available). (A transition density of 24 ppl/ha was assumed; detailed analysis could indicate higher or lower percentages of dwellings suitable for GSHPs or TNs.) In areas where TNs are implemented instead of ASHPs, the peak power requirement for heating could be as low as 5% of what ASHPs would require, depending on choice or availability of heat sources and strategic design of thermal energy storage.

While Section 2 presented data on the numbers of dwellings of different types in the LDC, no comparable data was available for non-residential buildings. From province-wide natural gas consumption data, as noted in the main Two Pathways report, about 47% of natural gas used for space heating in Ontario is for the residential sector, with the remainder for other sectors (commercial (including institutional), industrial (including power generation)).

The simplifying assumption was made that residential buildings are responsible for 47% of heating demand in each LDC – not just province-wide – and that the temporal variation of heating demand is similar for dwellings with and without smart meters. The mix of customers shown in Section 3 may provide some indication regarding the validity of this assumption, but without an hourly (or monthly) breakdown it is not possible to know what portion of energy consumed for uses other than residential is for space heating. (The LDC will likely have the data needed to make that determination, as part of a local heating planning initiative.) If, for example, residential buildings are responsible for 70% of heating demand in the LDC instead of 47%, then the heating power demand estimate made here will be too high by a factor of $70/47 = 1.49$.

Supported by data from the Comprehensive Energy Use Database (CEUD),⁷ the average efficiency of conversion of natural gas energy to thermal energy (e.g., with gas furnaces) was assumed to be 85%. Combining population-weighted, province-wide HDH with monthly natural gas usage for space heating then allowed determination of the province-wide thermal energy (MWh) per HDH needed to heat all buildings. This was scaled down according to the LDC's population and local HDH to estimate the *thermal energy per HDH* (MW) needed within the LDC to heat buildings in any given hour. Using heat pumps to provide that much thermal power would require less electrical power, with the reduction factor being $1/\text{COP}$ where COP is the instantaneous effective COP of the GSHP or ASHP.

For GSHPs it has been assumed that $\text{COP} = 3$. Full decarbonization of heating with ASHPs generally

⁷ https://oee.nrcan.gc.ca/corporate/statistics/neud/dpa/menus/trends/comprehensive_tables/list.cfm

requires the use of electric resistance supplementary heating, for when it is very cold and the ASHP cannot provide adequate heat. The effective COP is referred to as COP_{adj} in the main Two Pathways report, which describes the detailed model used for COP_{adj} .

Taking into account all of the above allowed estimation of the electricity demand that would have resulted if all buildings in the LDC (based on 2021 data) had been heated with heat pumps instead of fossil fuel during the years 2018 through 2023. The percentages of GSHPs and ASHPs are based on population density, as discussed above. The resulting hourly electric power demands – for space heating alone, since data for actual hourly demand was not available – are shown in Figure 6. No attempt has been made to project into the future; population growth and electrification of other sectors (transportation, industry) would cause further increases in power demand.

It must be emphasized that the approximations and assumptions involved, and discussed above, mean that the overall magnitude of the estimated power demand for the LDC is uncertain, perhaps at the $\pm 40\%$ level. But the hourly fluctuations should be much more reliable – perhaps $\pm 10\%$.

Data on actual 2021 electric energy consumption (including a breakdown by rate class or connection type) and summer and winter peak power are provided by the OEB in its General Statistics yearbook.⁸ For a small number of LDCs, there is limited or no data. Table 6 shows the data provided for Orangeville Hydro Limited, with N/A indicating “not available”. Where data is available, it may provide some insight into the validity or warranted adjustment to the assumption that residential building are responsible for 47% of the heat demand. Detailed (hourly) consumption data held by the LDC would be even more useful.

Table 6

Rate Class / Description	Units	Value (2021)
General Service < 50 kW	MWh	33534
General Service >= 50 kW	MWh	130760
Large User	MWh	0
Residential	MWh	95087
Sentinel Lighting Connections	MWh	102
Street Lighting Connections	MWh	870
Unmetered Scattered Load Connections	MWh	375
Embedded Distributor(s)	MWh	0
Sub Transmission Customers	MWh	0
Total Consumption	MWh	260728
Winter Peak	MW	41.9
Summer Peak	MW	49.8

⁸ <https://www.oeb.ca/sites/default/files/yearbook-General-Statistics-2021.xlsx>

Figure 6. An estimate of what the hourly electric power demand for electrified heating with ASHPs and GSHPs would have been over a six year period if all existing buildings in the LDC had been converted from non-electric heating in the percentages indicated. Extreme peaks in power for ASHPs correspond to very cold weather, when the ASHP effective COP drops to close to 1. If available, actual (summer) peak and mean power for the LDC in 2021 are indicated by horizontal solid and dashed cyan lines.

8. Discussion

Through extensive analysis of available data, an estimate has been developed for the hourly electric power demand that might result from heating electrification of all buildings in the LDC. The model employs a mix of air-source and ground-source heat pumps, with GSHPs assumed wherever census data indicates that there should be sufficient space to install ground heat exchangers.

Due to use of approximations and reasonable assumptions in the modeling, necessitated by inadequate data, the overall magnitude of the estimated electric power demand in Figure 6 is uncertain at the $\pm 40\%$ level. Data held by the LDC, Enbridge, MPAC, etc. would be required to derive a less uncertain estimate. Nonetheless, more accurate modeling will not change the characteristics of power demand versus temperature for ASHPs, including extreme peaks.

Although it varies by LDC, the annual heating degree hours for buildings across Ontario are roughly 10 times the annual cooling degree hours. The maximum hourly heating degrees (in the coldest weather)

are about 3.5 times the maximum hourly cooling degrees.

Equipment used for cooling will generally have a COP of 3 (as high as 5) on hot days, while ASHPs have $COP_{adj} \sim 1$ on very cold days. This means that the peak electric power demand for heating buildings with ASHPs in the coldest weather will be about 10 times the peak electric power demand for cooling the same buildings. GSHPs maintain a fairly constant COP, independent of the outdoor temperature but dropping slightly as the ground temperature drops. Peak electric power demand for GSHPs in the coldest weather will be about 3.5 times the peak electric power demand for cooling the same buildings.

All the areas (census DBs) where ASHPs were assumed in the above modeling should have sufficiently dense heat demand for thermal networks to be viable. Providing decarbonized heating with TNs instead of ASHPs would avoid the modeled power demand for ASHPs (Figure 6). Electricity needed for TNs is relatively minor.

Of particular concern to the LDC will be the need to greatly increase the peak power capacity on the local distribution network if significant numbers of customers attempt to decarbonize their heating by converting to ASHPs. Utilization of capacity added to accommodate ASHPs could be as low as 8 percent.

Analysis in the main Two Pathways report indicates that, when the cost of providing peak power for ASHPs is properly included, the societal cost of heating with TNs will be far less than the societal cost of heating with ASHPs. The cost of additional power system capacity (generation, transmission and distribution) to provide reliable peak power for heating decarbonization with ASHPs (including electric resistance backup) is likely to be several times what building owners pay to install the ASHPs. Unless retail electricity rate structures are changed to charge separately for energy and peak capacity (whether used or not), rates per kWh will rise and customers who do not install ASHPs will end up subsidizing customers who do.

Given the great difference of their peak power requirements, installation of GSHPs instead of ASHPs should be strongly encouraged wherever TN service is not viable or unlikely to be available in the foreseeable future and there is sufficient land available for the ground heat exchangers.

Deployment of TNs in higher density areas, including for existing detached homes, warrants careful consideration to avoid the severe increased peak power demand and power system costs that would likely result from an attempt to achieve large-scale decarbonization with ASHPs.

In the short term, before TN service can be made available, customers who wish to install ASHPs should be encouraged to install units that are sized for cooling and to switch over to fuel-based heating systems at temperatures below about +4 C. See Section 7 of the main Two Pathways report for more on this strategy.

Orangeville Hydro Limited: statistical deviation of observed from fitted kWh
(2018,2019,2020,2021,2022,2023), dows = 123, tc = 18.0 hours

